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ECS social media policy

eucitsciproject

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General principles

The European Citizen Science social media policy is an integral part of the [ECS communication and dissemination plan](#) and is a direct application of it. All communications must follow the general principles, objectives, messages, audiences and be coherent with the ECS vision and mission.

ECS Vision

A globally connected, inclusive and strong citizen science community for societal change in Europe

ECS Mission

Creating and sharing data, resources, training and services with communities involved in citizen science, building capacity, and uniting diverse European actors under a common platform.

The European Citizen Science 5Cs mission

Creating and sharing of citizen science data and knowledge

Capacity building and training services

Common platform uniting diverse European actors

Contributing to European policy making

Changing today's societal challenges into future opportunities through citizen science

Social media channel

The European Citizen Science project has inherited the social media channels of the EU-Citizen.Science project (LinkedIn, Bluesky, Facebook, Instagram) and will continue to be present on social media.

Platform	Handle
LinkedIn	@eucitsci
Bluesky	@eucitsciproject
Facebook	@EUCitSciProject
Instagram	@eucitsciproject

Hashtags (examples)

#CitizenScience #community #engagement #training #platform #diversity #inclusion #europe #OpenScience

Tone of voice

The tone of voice can be slightly different across different media and channels, especially when targeting different audiences that require diverse vocabulary, but should always be consistent. Every spokesperson should be familiar with the ECS tone of voice and keep it in mind when writing and speaking. See chapter 4.1 ECS tone of voice of the ECS communication and dissemination plan.

Community-oriented

Keywords: familiar, personal, engaging

Authoritative and evidence-based

Keywords: reliable, evidenced-based, understandable

Focused on diversity

Keywords: inclusiveness, diversity

International and connected

Keywords: shared, international, global

Passionate

Keywords: enthusiasm, human, motivating

Responsibility

All social media channels are managed by the ECS Communication team.

Every partner is urged to share, like, repost all content published in the ECS social media channels.

Every partner is invited to contribute to the social media production and update the calendar.

Every partner informs the ECS Communication team when they are about to share any major-impact content.

Every partner must respect confidentiality regarding our project's internal information.

When posting on their own social media channels any content that is connected with the project, all partners must tag the European Citizen Science project (see Table 1) and all partners involved, and describe the content with the appropriate hashtags in order to give maximum visibility.

Conduct

We are **respectful, polite** and **patient**, when engaging in conversations on our project's behalf.

We **avoid speaking on matters outside our field of expertise**. Everyone should be careful not to answer questions or make statements that fall under somebody else's responsibility.

We follow our **confidentiality policy and data protection policy** contained in the ECS project handbook and observe laws on copyright, trademarks, plagiarism and fair use.

We **don't delete or ignore comments for no reason**. They should be listened to and we must reply to criticism.

We **never post discriminatory, offensive or libelous content and commentary**. Discriminatory, offensive or libelous commentaries will be immediately deleted.

Content involving people or other projects and initiatives cannot be published without the **explicit consent** of the interested parties.

We **correct or remove any misleading or false content** as quickly as possible.

Social media crisis

A social media crisis is any activity on social platforms that may impact our project's reputation in a negative way, sparked anger, disappointment, or distrust on a wide scale. If left unaddressed, it could have major long-term consequences for our project, partners and community.

How to behave in case of a communication crisis:

- Respond promptly
- Engage with comments with empathy
- Be frank and informative
- Update all relevant parties
- Take responsibility and implement the necessary actions in case of violation of rules or laws. Make them public.